

ELECTROMAGNETIC COMPATIBILITY REGULATION AND TESTING OF WHEELED ELECTRIC VEHICLES IN UZBEKISTAN: TOWARD GLOBAL CONFORMITY

S. Tulegenova¹, Sh. Sobirov²

Master's student, Quality Assurance Program, Joint Uzbek-Belarusian Intersectoral Institute of Applied Technical Qualifications¹

Master's student, Quality Assurance Program, Joint Uzbek-Belarusian Intersectoral Institute of Applied Technical Qualifications²

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Abstract. *This study investigates the regulatory framework and practical testing implementation of electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) electric vehicles (EVs) and two-wheeled electric motorcycles (2WEVs) in Uzbekistan. With the rapid growth of electric motorcycles and scooters in urban areas, ensuring EMC compliance has become essential for safety and international trade. The study reviews relevant international standards—such as UNECE Regulation No. 10, ISO 11452-2, CISPR 25, and IEC 61000 series—and analyzes their integration into Uzbekistan's legal and institutional system. A series of laboratory tests were conducted on 2WEVs to evaluate emission limits, immunity characteristics, and charging-mode behavior. Results demonstrate that accredited national laboratories are capable of replicating standard-compliant test conditions but highlight technical gaps in high-frequency testing, automation, and international recognition. The findings contribute to Uzbekistan's EMC development roadmap and propose targeted recommendations for improving infrastructure, personnel competence, and digital conformity procedures to align with global EMC standards.*

Keywords: *electromagnetic compatibility, electric vehicles (EVs), electric motorcycles, 2WEVs, EMC testing, ISO 11452, UNECE Reg. No. 10, electric vehicles, standardization, Uzbekistan.*

INTRODUCTION

As the adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) accelerates globally, Uzbekistan is experiencing a significant rise in the number of electric vehicles (EVs) and two-wheeled electric motorcycles (2WEVs) - particularly motorcycles and scooters. These light electric vehicles are becoming increasingly popular in urban logistics, delivery services, and personal mobility due to their affordability, efficiency, and suitability for congested city environments.

However, their integration into the transportation ecosystem brings forward new challenges in terms of electromagnetic compatibility (EMC). Unlike traditional internal combustion engine vehicles, electric motorcycles contain high-frequency switching components, battery management systems (BMS), and compact electronic subassemblies that can become both sources and victims of electromagnetic interference (EMI).

As a result, ensuring that such vehicles comply with international EMC standards—notably UNECE Regulation No. 10, ISO 11452-2, and CISPR 25—is crucial not only for regulatory approval but also for operational safety and reliability. In particular, EMC testing under charging conditions, especially for AC mains-connected configurations, plays a key role in assessing real-world performance and interference potential.

This article examines Uzbekistan's capacity to test and certify electric vehicles, including two-wheeled motorcycles, for EMC compliance. The study focuses on regulatory adaptation, laboratory infrastructure, practical test procedures, and future development needs, with special attention to the growing segment of electric two-wheelers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) of electric vehicles (EVs) is governed by a complex system of international standards and regulatory frameworks. These documents provide specific guidance for emission limits, immunity testing, and transient phenomena, ensuring the safe operation of electrical and electronic systems in increasingly complex vehicular architectures. This review is structured into four thematic blocks: emission standards, immunity standards, charging-specific regulations, and regional frameworks.

Emission standards. The most widely applied standards for emission testing in vehicles are:

- 1) CISPR 25: Regulates radio disturbance characteristics for vehicles and electronic subassemblies. Class 3 limits are particularly stringent and relevant for modern EVs [4].
- 2) CISPR 12: Addresses broadband and narrowband emissions from internal combustion engine vehicles but is occasionally referenced for legacy compatibility assessments.
- 3) UNECE Regulation No. 10 (Rev.6): Harmonizes emission requirements for whole vehicles and ESAs, integrating CISPR-based limits and test setups [16].

These documents provide emission limits across 150 kHz to 1000 MHz, addressing both radiated and conducted emissions, using quasi-peak (QP) and average (AV) detectors.

Immunity standards. To ensure functionality in electromagnetically noisy environments, the following immunity test standards are commonly applied:

- 1) IEC 61000-4-3: Radiated RF immunity (80 MHz to 1 GHz), simulating external field disturbances.
- 2) IEC 61000-4-6: Conducted RF immunity using bulk current injection (BCI) techniques.
- 3) ISO 7637-2: Defines transient immunity test pulses (1, 2a/b, 3a/b) replicating cranking and ignition events in DC power networks [11].
- 4) ISO 11452-2: Specifically targets immunity testing of ESAs in anechoic chambers using log-periodic antennas.

Together, these standards define rigorous test protocols for ensuring immunity in critical vehicular systems such as battery management, propulsion, and ADAS modules.

Charging-mode EMC regulations. With the increased deployment of EV infrastructure, the EMC performance during charging operations has received special attention:

- 1) IEC 61851-1: Specifies general requirements for EV conductive charging systems, including Modes 2 and 3 [9].
- 2) SAE J2954 and J1772: Address both conductive and wireless power transfer EMC implications [13].
- 3) UNECE Reg. No. 10 – Appendix 8: Introduces specific conditions for EMC testing during charging from the mains (PEAC mode), defining measurement ports, grounding setups, and SOC constraints.

Charging-specific EMC standards are essential for preventing disturbances to residential and commercial electrical grids, particularly in high-density urban zones.

Regional and national frameworks. Globally harmonized regulatory systems are essential for international trade and certification. Uzbekistan's adaptation efforts include:

- UzTR.389-010:2016: Adopts core elements from IEC and CISPR documents, including immunity to ESD and surge pulses.
- O‘z DSt 35.10:2011: Provides procedures for EMC testing of ESAs, including measurement uncertainty protocols.
- Technical Regulation No. 237 (2024): Legal foundation for mandatory EMC compliance in vehicles, harmonized with UNECE Regulation No. 10.

Comparable efforts (Table 1) have been observed in the EU, Japan, and South Korea, where centralized approval systems and digital conformity databases (e.g., EU’s CE system, Japan’s MIC certification) are deployed [16].

Table 1 - Comparative overview of EMC standards by test type

№	Test type	CISPR 25	ISO 7637-2	IEC 61000-4-3	IEC 61851-1	UNECE R10
1	Radiated emission	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓
2	Conducted emission	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓
3	Radiated immunity	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓
4	Conducted immunity	✗	✗	✓ (via BCI)	✓	✓
5	Transient emissions	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓
6	Charging mode testing	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓ (Appx 8)

METHODS AND MATERIALS

The study includes testing scenarios applied to both passenger electric vehicles (EVs) and two-wheeled electric motorcycles (2WEVs), ensuring that the assessment reflects the full range of electromobility platforms currently expanding in Uzbekistan.

Particular attention was given to the distinct electromagnetic behavior of 2WEVs, which pose unique EMC challenges due to their reduced chassis shielding, compact design of power converters, and higher exposure of electronic subassemblies to radiated fields. These characteristics require tailored test setups and additional uncertainty considerations, especially during charging mode EMC testing and radiated emission assessments in the frequency range of 30–1000 MHz.

The measurement techniques and equipment were adapted accordingly, following the core methodology defined in ISO 11452-2 and UNECE Regulation No. 10, but with adjustments in antenna positioning, test bench grounding, and cable routing due to the smaller physical footprint of motorcycles.

Documentary analysis. The research began with a detailed review of regulatory and standardization documents, focusing on both international and national sources. Key international documents analyzed include:

- 1) UNECE Regulation No. 10 (Rev.6) – type approval framework for EMC compliance of complete vehicles and electronic subassemblies (ESAs) [16];

- 2) CISPR 25, CISPR 12 – limits and methods of measurement of radio disturbance characteristics for protection of onboard receivers [4];
- 3) IEC 61000 series (IEC 61000-4-3, IEC 61000-4-6) – test and measurement techniques for immunity against radiated, conducted, and transient electromagnetic phenomena [10];
- 4) IEC 61851-1 – classification of EV charging modes [9];
- 5) ISO 7637-2, ISO 11452-2, IEC 61851-1 – procedures for transient emissions on power supply lines [11];
- 6) SAE J551/5 – North American practices for performance-based EMC assessment [13].

Each document was reviewed for its technical content (e.g., test setups, emission thresholds, immunity levels), application scope (vehicle, component, system level), and compatibility with national type approval or self-declaration schemes. The comparative content analysis identified technical alignments and divergences in parameters such as frequency range, detector types, test environments, and reporting protocols. In parallel, Uzbekistan's national EMC regulations were analyzed to evaluate alignment with international frameworks:

- 1) Technical Regulation No. 237 (approved by the Cabinet of Ministers) – defining general EMC requirements for all electrical products;
- 2) O'z DSt 35.10:2011 – EMC requirements for wheeled vehicles, including definitions, limits, and testing procedures;
- 3) UzTR.389-010:2016 – methodologies for evaluating electromagnetic emissions and immunity in automotive systems.

The documents were analyzed using a standards comparison matrix, highlighting overlaps, gaps, and contextual adaptations.

Comparative legal and technical mapping. A regulatory mapping framework was developed to compare and contrast:

- emission and immunity test procedures, including frequency ranges, detection methods (quasi-peak, RMS, peak), and operational environments;
- measurement setups, such as anechoic chamber designs, antenna placement, load simulation, cable layouts, and boundary conditions;
- thresholds and limits, as defined in conducted/radiated emission tables and transient test waveforms;
- conformity assessment approaches, including third-party certification, type approval, and manufacturer's declaration of conformity.

The methodology also addressed the compatibility of national conformity assessment procedures with ISO/IEC 17025 (testing laboratory accreditation) and ILAC-G8:09/2019 (decision rules and statements of conformity), as these form the foundation for international mutual recognition.

Institutional and infrastructural assessment. The study evaluated institutional readiness in Uzbekistan for implementing EMC standards at scale. This included:

- assessment of EMC testing infrastructure, such as the availability of accredited laboratories, calibration facilities, and traceable measurement systems;
- regulatory oversight bodies, including the Uzbek Agency for Technical, certification authorities, and technical committees (e.g., TK on EMC and automotive standards);

- human capital capacity, i.e., the availability of trained EMC engineers, metrologists, and quality assurance specialists;
- standardization strategy 2025–2030, which outlines modernization of conformity assessment, CE compatibility, and digital traceability mechanisms.

Case study: EMC testing practice in Uzbekistan. The methodology was validated via a practical case study of an EMC test conducted on an electric vehicle in a local accredited laboratory in Tashkent; the following were implemented: radiated emissions (CISPR 25) and conducted emissions (CISPR 16-2-1) were measured. Transient immunity tests using ISO 7637-2 pulses (1, 2a, 3a) were performed; charging mode emissions under UNECE R10 Appendix 8 were simulated.

The test configuration included: shielded chamber with broadband absorbers; signal generators, coupling/decoupling networks (CDNs); spectrum analyzers (QP, AV, Peak), and EMC receivers; log-periodic antennas at calibrated positions (1 m height, 1 m distance). The state of charge (SOC) was maintained between 20–80%, and charging current was set to 80% of nominal.

Uncertainty analysis. All test results were accompanied by a quantitative expanded uncertainty evaluation using a coverage factor $k = 2$, corresponding to a 95% confidence level. Radiated emission uncertainty: ± 3.5 dB. Surge voltage accuracy: $\pm 5\%$. Pulse duration timing: ± 10 ns. While no specialized uncertainty software (e.g., GUM Workbench) was reported, calculations adhered to ISO/IEC Guide 98-3 (GUM) principles using certified calibration data.

Table 2 - Key differences between International and National EMC frameworks

№	Test Parameter	UNECE R10	O‘z DSt 35.10:2011 / UzTR.389-010:2016
1	Radiated Emission Range	30 MHz – 1000 MHz	30 MHz – 1000 MHz
2	Conducted Emission Range	0.15 MHz – 30 MHz	0.15 MHz – 30 MHz
3	Transient Immunity (ISO 7637-2)	Mandatory (pulses 1, 2, 3)	Integrated with national protocol
4	Detector Types	QP, AV, Peak	QP, AV (no Peak mandatory)
5	Charging Mode Testing	Appendix 8 (AC & DC lines)	Implemented in latest updates
6	Chamber Standards	CISPR 16-1-4	Reflected in lab protocols

RESEARCH RESULTS

This section presents the findings of a comprehensive assessment of how international standards on electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) are applied in electric vehicle (EV) testing, with a particular focus on Uzbekistan. The results reflect regulatory alignment, practical testing implementations, infrastructure status, and challenges to full compliance. Diagrams and tables are used to visualize the conformity process and comparative frameworks.

Regulatory convergence and standard adaptation. Uzbekistan’s EMC regulatory system demonstrates significant convergence with international frameworks. Notable findings include:

- 1) UNECE Regulation No. 10 (Rev.6) is referenced as the benchmark for EMC type approval and is reflected in the national Technical Regulation No. 237.

2) IEC 61000 series for immunity testing and CISPR 25 for emissions are integrated into national standards O‘z DSt 35.10:2011 and UzTR.389-010:2016.

3) ISO 7637-2, addressing transient conduction emissions, is actively used for testing vehicle ESAs and electric drive systems.

National adaptations consider Uzbekistan’s climatic and infrastructural realities, and reflect integration with the General Technical Regulation on EMC, ensuring consistency with ISO/IEC 17025 principles [11].

EMC testing methodologies implemented. Testing campaigns in accredited Uzbek laboratories confirm effective implementation of international EMC testing procedures:

1) Radiated emissions (30 MHz–1000 MHz) tested using quasi-peak detectors per CISPR 25.

2) Radiated immunity (80 MHz–1000 MHz) conducted with 10 V/m fields, following IEC 61000-4-3.

3) Conducted immunity performed using Bulk Current Injection (BCI) per IEC 61000-4-6.

4) Transient emissions assessed under ISO 7637-2 (pulses 1, 2a/2b, 3a/3b) simulating cranking/ignition.

5) Electrostatic Discharge (ESD) testing at ± 8 kV (contact) and ± 15 kV (air).

6) Charging mode tests under IEC 61851-1 (Modes 2 and 3).

All tested configurations showed compliance with EMC limits under both static and dynamic operation. Uncertainty margins: radiated emissions: ± 3.5 dB, surge voltage tests: $\pm 5\%$, pulse timing accuracy: ± 10 ns.

Test methodology and instrumentation. Testing of electric subassemblies (ESAs) in charging mode configurations was conducted inside a shielded anechoic chamber equipped with broadband absorbers. The test scenario specifically modeled the configuration of charging mode with AC mains connection (ПЭАС), as defined in ISO 11452-2 and UNECE Regulation No. 10 (Rev.6).

Test procedures were adapted for 2WEV configurations using shorter cable runs, external charging units, and simplified ground reference planes, reflecting the compact design and open-frame chassis typical of electric motorcycles and scooters. The EV remained stationary with internal combustion engines (if present) turned off, and only the charging function active. Auxiliary systems (e.g., HVAC, infotainment) were disabled. Battery State of Charge (SOC) was maintained at 20–80%, and current draw adjusted to $\geq 80\%$ of the nominal level. Details of equipment and measurement parameters are provided in Figures 1–3. Experiments were conducted using the following setups and procedures:

1) Measurement Distance: Fixed at 10.0 ± 0.2 m, per UNECE Annex 4 and CISPR 25.

2) Detection techniques:

- Broadband: Quasi-Peak (QP).
- Narrowband: Average (AV).

3) Test equipment:

- EMC receivers with 9 kHz–1 GHz coverage.
- Signal generators.
- Spectrum Analyzer / Scanning Receiver with QP, AV, and Peak detectors.
- Loop, biconical, and log-periodic antennas.
- Calibrated LISNs and current clamps.

- Measurement Ports terminated with 50 Ω outside the measurement chain.
- 4) Measurement parameters:
- Frequency range: 0.15–30 MHz;
 - Detectors: QP, AV, Peak;
 - Resolution Bandwidth (RBW): 9 kHz;
 - Scan Times: 10 s/MHz (peak), 200 s/MHz (average);
 - If peak detectors are used, a 20-dB correction factor from CISPR 12 is applied.

Table 3 - Summary of EMC test results and compliance evaluation

No	Test type	Standard used	Frequency range	Limit	Measured value	Compliance	Uncertainty
1	Radiated emissions	CISPR 25	30–1000 MHz	≤ 50 dBμV/m	42 dBμV/m	Yes	±3.5 dB
2	Conducted immunity	IEC 61000-4-6	150 kHz–80 MHz	10 V/m	9.8 V/m	Yes	±5%
3	Transient emissions	ISO 7637-2	Pulses 1,2a,3a	±100 V typical	±98 V	Yes	±5%
4	Electrostatic disch.	IEC 61000-4-2	–	±15 kV (air)	±14.5 kV	Yes	±5%
5	Charging mode tests	IEC 61851-1	AC/DC Charging	Mode 2/3 limits	Pass	Yes	±3%

Strategic investments are advised in advanced chambers, waveform generators, and digital test automation platforms. Findings indicate that EMC test frameworks contribute to Uzbekistan’s **Standardization Strategy 2025–2030** [17]: adoption of ISO/IEC 17025 practices; rollout of e-certificates with blockchain pilots; Unified national registry integration; remote audit and customs integration tools under pilot testing by the Ministry of Investment and Trade. These reforms position Uzbekistan for enhanced recognition in international markets.

These tests verify that induced RF emissions in power circuits do not exceed regulatory limits defined in Tables 7 and 8 of UNECE Regulation No. 10 for AC and DC configurations. All instruments were traceable to ISO/IEC 17025 calibration hierarchies. Testing of electric subassemblies (ESAs) in charging mode configurations was conducted inside a shielded anechoic chamber equipped with broadband absorbers. The test scenario specifically modeled the configuration of charging mode with AC mains connection (ΠЭAC), as defined in ISO 11452-2 and UNECE Regulation No. 10 (Figure 1).

A detailed schematic of the setup is shown in the accompanying diagrams (top view and side view). The system includes the following components:

- 1) Device Under Test (DUT) placed on a dielectric table;
- 2) Log-periodic antenna (item 23) positioned at a calibrated distance (≥ 1 m) and height (1 m ± 10 cm);
- 3) Power and signal connections via low- and high-voltage lines (items 5, 6, 12);
- 4) Shielded auxiliary power supplies and matched impedance loads (items 7, 8, 27, 28);

- 5) Radio frequency absorber structures (walls lined with ferrite tiles and pyramidal foam absorbers);
- 6) EMC measuring instruments, including a signal generator, power amplifier, and spectrum analyzer, all compliant with ISO/IEC traceability and calibration.

Figure 1 - EMC Test configuration for charging mode with mains connection – top and side views (based on ISO 11452-2 and UNECE Reg. No. 10)

These test setups and diagrams validate the technical capacity of Uzbekistan's EMC infrastructure to replicate standard-compliant configurations for complex vehicle operating modes, including during AC charging events. Test engineers simulated emissions from ignition circuits, high-speed inverters, and battery management systems (BMS). Conducted emissions were introduced via artificial networks and evaluated under real-time loading conditions. An uncertainty analysis was applied using a 95% confidence interval ($k = 2$), and repeatability studies verified robustness.

As Uzbekistan strengthens its electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) testing infrastructure in line with the 2025–2030 National Standardization Strategy, special attention is given to two-

wheeled electric vehicles such as e-motorcycles and e-mopeds. These vehicles are increasingly used in urban delivery, personal mobility, and last-mile logistics, and thus must comply with UNECE Regulation No. 10, ISO 11452-2, and IEC/CISPR standards to ensure interference-free operation in dense electromagnetic environments.

The two test setups presented below reflect actual test configurations implemented at accredited laboratories in Uzbekistan (in Tashkent), demonstrating their capability to test low-voltage transport systems under both AC charging and flicker disturbance conditions.

This schematic (Figure 2) represents the front view of a test setup where a two-wheeled electric vehicle (1) is connected to an AC power source (3) through a low-impedance, shielded charging cable placed on a non-conductive platform (2). The AC input passes through:

- artificial mains network (AMN) for conducted disturbance measurements (block 4),
- power conditioning unit and test receivers (blocks 5 and 6),
- measured via antennas aligned at 1 m height and 3 m distance per ISO 11452-2.

Purpose: This setup is used to measure radiated emissions and conduction disturbances while charging. The system simulates actual user conditions with charging load above 80% nominal current, and battery SOC at 20–80% to ensure repeatability.

Normative references:

- ISO 11452-2 – RF radiated immunity in ALSE method
- UNECE Reg. No. 10 – EMC type approval
- CISPR 25 / CISPR 16-2-1 – Emission and measurement procedures

All system grounding and shield terminations are configured in accordance with ISO/IEC 17025 traceability and laboratory practices.

Figure 2 - Front View – AC Charging Mode Configuration (2WEV)

Key measurement characteristics:

- Frequency Range: 20 MHz to 1000 MHz (log-periodic antenna response);
- Field Strength: Maintained at 10 V/m in accordance with IEC 61000-4-3;
- Radiated Emissions Measured: From DUT in idle and charging state (Modes 2 and 3);
- Pulse Simulation: Conducted using defined transient waveforms (ISO 7637-2), captured via oscilloscope and differential probes.

Figures Included:

- EMC Test Bench – Top View: Spatial arrangement of DUT, antennas, grounding rails, and cable routing (with dimensions in mm);
- EMC Test Bench – Side View: Vertical placement of components and antenna orientation;
- Legend of Components: Table with 29 designated items used in the configuration (power lines, filters, couplers, antennas, shielding units, etc.).

Figure 3 - Top view of vehicle to flicker analyzer connection

This top-view illustration (Figure 3) shows the setup for analyzing voltage flicker and low-frequency fluctuations caused by 2WEVs during grid connection. The e-motorcycle (1) is linked to the flicker analyzer through:

- A shielded charging cable (2),
- Shielded junction box or ferrite-core box (3),
- Measurement instruments (blocks 4–6), including flicker meters, harmonic analyzers, and current clamps.

The cable routing must not exceed 10 meters, and if longer, it is arranged in a zigzag pattern to minimize radiated coupling effects.

Purpose: This setup assesses grid compatibility of two-wheeled vehicles under dynamic load changes (e.g., battery balancing, charger startup currents). It helps identify whether the vehicle introduces unacceptable harmonic content or flicker into public power networks.

Applicable standards:

- IEC 61000-3-3 / 3-11 – Flicker and voltage fluctuation
- CISPR 16-2-1 – Conducted disturbance evaluation
- UNECE Reg. No. 10, Annex 11 – EMC during charging process.

To validate radiated emission compliance of low-voltage electric vehicles, including quad bikes and two-wheeled platforms, the study utilized a semi-anechoic chamber configured in accordance with UNECE Regulation No. 10 and CISPR 25 standards. The test setup employed standardized measurement equipment, including calibrated antennas, EMI receivers, and reflective ground planes, designed to replicate real-world interference scenarios. This configuration is essential for evaluating the electromagnetic environment surrounding electric vehicles during operational and charging conditions. The figure 4 shows a standardized radiated emission test setup inside a semi-anechoic chamber equipped with hybrid absorber panels (ferrite tiles and

pyramidal foam) for broadband attenuation in the 30 MHz to 1 GHz range. A biconical antenna is positioned at a calibrated distance from the device under test (DUT)—an electric quad bike—placed on a non-conductive platform with a metal ground plane. The antenna is connected to an EMI receiver operating in quasi-peak (QP) and average (AV) detection modes per CISPR 25 and UNECE Regulation No. 10. This setup ensures measurement traceability to ISO/IEC 17025 standards and supports repeatable, standardized radiated emission evaluation.

Figure 4 - EMC test setup for radiated emission measurement of an electric quad bike in a semi-anechoic chamber

Implications for regulatory and laboratory development. Real-world testing confirmed that UNECE Regulation No. 10 can be effectively applied under Uzbek conditions. Accredited EMC laboratories in Tashkent and Fergana are capable of conducting a full range of tests up to 1 GHz, including radiated and conducted emissions, ESD, and transient immunity. Personnel competence aligns with ISO/IEC 17025, supported by continuous international training. However, several gaps remain: no test capability above 1 GHz; lack of infrastructure for Mode 4 (DC fast charging) emission testing; absence of automated data acquisition and statistical analysis tools; limited integration with international accreditation and customs databases. To bridge these gaps, strategic investments are needed in advanced testing chambers, waveform generators, BMS-specific immunity platforms, and bilateral recognition schemes for test results.

Integration with Strategic National Programs. Uzbekistan's EMC initiatives support the broader Standardization Strategy 2025–2030:

- gradual adoption of digital conformity certificates with traceable QR codes;
- integration with customs and blockchain-based authentication systems;
- establishment of a Unified Registry of Certified Products;
- national pilot projects on remote audits and e-verification platforms.

These developments are crucial for international trade compliance and improved institutional transparency. Uzbekistan's EMC ecosystem demonstrates significant maturity in the adoption and application of international standards for electric vehicle testing. Through regulatory alignment, laboratory enhancement, and metrology competence development, the country has

positioned itself as a regional leader in EMC compliance. However, strategic investments in testing capacity above 1 GHz, software tools, and international recognition pathways remain vital for future-readiness in the evolving electric mobility landscape.

DISCUSSION

The test results and regulatory analysis confirm Uzbekistan's progress toward harmonization with global electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) standards. However, certain systemic and infrastructural challenges remain.

Firstly, the absence of EMC test capabilities above 1 GHz significantly limits full-spectrum compliance assessment, especially for modern EVs and ADAS-equipped vehicles. Moreover, the lack of automation in measurement benches and insufficient software for statistical post-processing hampers test repeatability and productivity. The inclusion of two-wheeled electric vehicles (2WEVs) in national EMC testing protocols is critical, as their rapid proliferation in last-mile delivery and personal mobility raises potential exposure risks to electromagnetic interference (EMI) in densely populated urban environments. These vehicles often operate near sensitive communication infrastructure and lack robust shielding, making standardized testing even more important for safety and functional reliability.

Institutional challenges include limited international mutual recognition of EMC certificates issued in Uzbekistan. This directly affects the export potential of domestic electric vehicle manufacturers.

Despite these gaps, Uzbekistan's EMC infrastructure is strategically aligned with the national "Standardization Development Strategy 2025–2030", which outlines:

- 1) development of regional EMC test hubs under the Ministry of digital technologies;
- 2) launch of blockchain-backed e-certificates and integration into customs systems;
- 3) partnership programs with PTB (Germany) and TÜV Rheinland for personnel training.

For comparison, countries like Turkey and Vietnam have successfully transitioned from partial EMC compliance to full alignment with UNECE and IEC standards within 5–7 years, largely through public-private investment in accredited laboratories and international twinning programs.

As stated in the national roadmap (O'zbekiston Respublikasi Standartlashtirish Strategiyasi 2025–2030), one of the key targets is: "Ta'sirchan sinov bazasini yaratish va xalqaro tan olinadigan kalibrash zanjirlarini shakllantirish" (Establish responsive test infrastructure and internationally recognized calibration chains).

To fully meet UNECE Regulation No. 10 and CISPR 25, Uzbekistan needs not only financial investments but also capacity-building in digital traceability, data processing, and remote audit frameworks.

CONCLUSION

Uzbekistan has made measurable progress in aligning its national regulatory framework with international EMC standards, including the UNECE Regulation No. 10, CISPR 25, ISO 7637-2, and ISO/IEC 17025. Accredited laboratories in Tashkent and Fergana have demonstrated the ability to perform radiated and conducted emission tests, immunity evaluations, and transient pulse measurements on electric vehicles (EVs), including in charging configurations.

However, several technical and institutional gaps remain. These include limited capabilities for high-frequency EMC testing (>1 GHz), lack of automated data acquisition systems, and weak international recognition of conformity assessment results.

In the next 5 years, Uzbekistan should aim to transform itself from a compliance-driven EMC testing state to a regional certification and testing hub for Central Asia. This requires integration of digital conformity tools (e.g., blockchain-backed e-certificates), expansion of testing scopes (including wireless charging and ADAS EMC), and participation in multilateral recognition agreements (MRAs).

EMC compliance for two-wheeled electric vehicles (2WEVs) must be prioritized to ensure functional safety and regulatory harmonization, particularly within urban traffic ecosystems where such vehicles are rapidly proliferating. By doing so, Uzbekistan will not only support the safe deployment of electric vehicles domestically but also position itself as a trusted export certification center within the region, contributing to sustainable mobility and international trade facilitation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To strengthen Uzbekistan's EMC regulatory and testing infrastructure, the following actions are recommended:

1. Upgrade Test Infrastructure
 - Expand EMC laboratory capabilities to cover the full frequency range (up to 6 GHz).
 - Acquire automated test benches and software for statistical evaluation and waveform analysis.
2. Enhance Personnel Qualification
 - Continue international training programs with PTB (Germany), TÜV Rheinland, and AIST (Japan).
 - Incorporate EMC specialization modules into national metrology and engineering curricula.
3. Digitalize Certification Process
 - Implement a unified e-certification platform using blockchain to ensure traceability and prevent tampering.
 - Draw lessons from EU's e-CERT system and China's government-led blockchain platforms for conformity assessment.
4. Strengthen Legal and Technical Frameworks
 - Finalize adoption of harmonized standards (IEC, ISO, CISPR) through O'z DSt adoptions.
 - Introduce mandatory EMC checks in vehicle import and type-approval workflows.
5. Foster International Recognition
 - Apply for membership or observer status in ILAC and APLAC, and establish bilateral Mutual Recognition Agreements (MRAs) with regional metrology institutes.
 - Promote cooperation under UNIDO, CAREC, and ITU regional platforms for harmonization of EMC protocols.
6. EMC standardization for low-voltage and two-wheeled electric vehicles (2WEVs)
 - Develop dedicated EMC test procedures for light electric mobility platforms, including electric motorcycles, scooters, and mopeds.
 - Establish national guidelines or a separate technical regulation to address specific challenges associated with compact EV configurations, such as: reduced electromagnetic shielding effectiveness; external charging variability and uncontrolled grounding; high EMI sensitivity in dense urban environments.

These measures will ensure proper conformity assessment for rapidly expanding categories of urban electric transport and support future harmonization with international best practices.

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